

Appendices

Appendix A: studies included in the systematic review

1. Adlakha, D.; Parra, D. C. Mind the gap: gender differences in walkability, transportation, and physical activity in urban India. *Journal of Transport & Health*, v. 18, 2020.
2. Adlakha, D. et al. "Can we walk?" environmental supports for physical activity in India. *Preventive Medicine*, v. 103, p. S81–S89, 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2016.09.020>.
3. Boakye-Dankwa, E. et al. Walking behaviour and patterns of perceived access to neighbourhood destinations in older adults from a low-density (Brisbane, Australia) and an ultra-dense city (Hong Kong, China). *Cities*, v. 84, p. 23–33, 2019.
4. Boulange, C. et al. Examining associations between urban design attributes and transport mode choice for walking, cycling, public transport, and private motor vehicle trips. *Journal of Transport & Health*, v. 6, p. 155–166, 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2017.07.007>.
5. Campos-Sánchez, F. S. et al. A GIS-based method for analysing the association between school-built environment and home-school route measures with active commuting to school in urban children and adolescents. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, v. 17, n. 7, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17072295>.
6. Carlson, J. A. et al. Work and home neighborhood design and physical activity. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, v. 32, n. 8, p. 1723–1729, 2018. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0890117118768767>.
7. Cervero, R.; Duncan, M. Walking, bicycling, and urban landscapes: evidence from the San Francisco Bay Area. *American Journal of Public Health*, v. 93, n. 9, p. 1478–1483, 2003. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.93.9.1478>.
8. Cheng, L. et al. Examining non-linear built environment effects on elderly's walking: a random forest approach. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, v. 88, 2020.
9. Christiansen, L. B. et al. International comparisons of the associations between objective measures of the built environment and transport-related walking and cycling: IPEN adult study. *Journal of Transport & Health*, v. 3, n. 4, p. 467–478, 2016. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2016.02.010>.
10. Chum, A.; Atkinson, P.; O'Campo, P. Does time spent in the residential neighbourhood moderate the relationship between neighbourhood walkability and transport-related walking? A cross-sectional study from Toronto, Canada. *BMJ Open*, v. 9, n. 4, 2019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-023598>.
11. Coughenour, C.; de la Fuente-Mella, H.; Paz, A. Analysis of self-reported walking for transit in a sprawling urban metropolitan area in the western U.S. *Sustainability*, v. 11, n. 3, 2019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11030852>.

12. Deforche, B. et al. Perceived social and physical environmental correlates of physical activity in older adolescents and the moderating effect of self-efficacy. *Preventive Medicine*, v. 50, p. S24–S29, 2010.
13. Dias, A. F. et al. Mediation role of residential density on the association between perceived environmental factors and active commuting to school in Brazilian adolescents. *Cadernos de Saúde Pública*, v. 37, n. 5, 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/0102-311X00067620>.
14. Dias, A. F. et al. Neighborhood environmental factors associated with leisure walking in adolescents. *Revista de Saúde Pública*, v. 54, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.11606/S1518-8787.2020054002222>.
15. Duncan, M. J. et al. Relationships of land use mix with walking for transport: do land uses and geographical scale matter? *Journal of Urban Health*, v. 87, n. 5, p. 782–795, 2010. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11524-010-9488-7>.
16. Etminani-Ghasrodashti, R.; Paydar, M.; Hamidi, S. University-related travel behavior: young adults' decision-making in Iran. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, v. 43, p. 495–508, 2018.
17. Ferrari, G. et al. Association between perceived neighborhood built environment and walking and cycling for transport among inhabitants from Latin America: the ELANS study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, v. 17, n. 18, p. 1–19, 2020.
18. Gehrke, S. R.; Wang, L. M. Operationalizing the neighborhood effects of the built environment on travel behavior. *Journal of Transport Geography*, v. 82, 2020.
19. Gehrke, S. R.; Clifton, K. J. Operationalizing land use diversity at varying geographic scales and its connection to mode choice: evidence from Portland, Oregon. *Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board*, v. 2453, n. 1, p. 128–136, 2014. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3141/2453-16>.
20. Gehrke, S. R.; Clifton, K. J. An activity-related land use mix construct and its connection to pedestrian travel. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, v. 46, n. 1, p. 9–26, 2019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2399808317690157>.
21. Habibian, M.; Hosseinzadeh, A. Walkability index across trip purposes. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, v. 42, p. 216–225, 2018.
22. Hatamzadeh, Y.; Hosseinzadeh, A. Toward a deeper understanding of elderly walking for transport: an analysis across genders in a case study of Iran. *Journal of Transport and Health*, v. 19, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2020.100949>.
23. He, H. et al. Associations between built environment characteristics and walking in older adults in a high-density city: a study from a Chinese megacity. *Frontiers in Public Health*, v. 8, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.00069>.
24. Im, H. N.; Choi, C. G. The hidden side of the entropy-based land-use mix index: clarifying the relationship between pedestrian volume and land-use mix. *Urban Studies*, v. 56, n. 9, p. 1865–1881, 2019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098018779708>.
25. Im, H. N.; Choi, C. G. Measuring pedestrian volume by land use mix: presenting a new entropy-based index by weighting walking generation units. *Environment*

- and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, v. 47, n. 7, p. 1219–1236, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2399808318824112>.
26. Ito, K. et al. Built environment and walking to school: findings from a student travel behavior survey in Massachusetts. *Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board*, v. 2666, p. 78–84, 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3141/2666-09>.
 27. Jiao, J. C. et al. Exploring effective built environment factors for evaluating pedestrian volume in high-density areas: a new finding for the central business district in Melbourne, Australia. *Land*, v. 10, n. 6, 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/land10060622>.
 28. Kerr, J. et al. Perceived neighborhood environmental attributes associated with walking and cycling for transport among adult residents of 17 cities in 12 countries: the IPEN study. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, v. 124, n. 3, p. 290–298, 2016. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1409466>.
 29. Kim, T.; Sohn, D.-W.; Choo, S. An analysis of the relationship between pedestrian traffic volumes and built environment around metro stations in Seoul. *KSCE Journal of Civil Engineering*, v. 21, n. 4, p. 1443–1452, 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12205-016-0915-5>.
 30. Larrañaga, A. M.; Cybis, H. B. B. The relationship between built environment and walking for different trip purposes in Porto Alegre, Brazil. *International Journal of Sustainable Development and Planning*, v. 9, n. 4, p. 568–580, 2014. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2495/SDP-V9-N4-568-580>.
 31. Li, F. et al. Built environment, adiposity, and physical activity in adults aged 50–75. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, v. 35, n. 1, p. 38–46, 2008. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2008.03.021>.
 32. Liu, J. X. et al. A tale of two social groups in Xiamen, China: trip frequency of migrants and locals and its determinants. *Travel Behaviour and Society*, v. 20, p. 213–224, 2020.
 33. Lu, Y. et al. The association of built environment and physical activity in older adults: using a citywide public housing scheme to reduce residential self-selection bias. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, v. 15, n. 9, 2018. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15091973>.
 34. Lu, Y.; Xiao, Y.; Ye, Y. Urban density, diversity and design: is more always better for walking? A study from Hong Kong. *Preventive Medicine*, v. 103, p. S99–S103, 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2016.08.042>.
 35. Manaugh, K.; Kreider, T. What is mixed use? Presenting an interaction method for measuring land use mix. *Journal of Transport and Land Use*, v. 6, n. 1, p. 63–72, 2013. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5198/jtlu.v6i1.291>.
 36. Manoj, M.; Verma, A. Effect of built environment measures on trip distance and mode choice decision of non-workers from a city of a developing country, India. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, v. 46, p. 351–364, 2016. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2016.04.013>.
 37. Mavoa, S. et al. Identifying appropriate land-use mix measures for use in a national walkability index. *Journal of Transport and Land Use*, v. 11, n. 1, p. 681–700, 2018.

38. McConville, M. E. et al. Disaggregate land uses and walking. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, v. 40, n. 1, p. 25–32, 2011. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2010.09.023>.
39. Mertens, L. et al. Individual, social, and physical environmental factors related to changes in walking and cycling for transport among older adults: a longitudinal study. *Health & Place*, v. 55, p. 120–127, 2019.
40. Moudon, A. V. et al. Attributes of environments supporting walking. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, v. 21, n. 5, p. 448–459, 2007. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4278/0890-1171-21.5.448>.
41. Noordzij, J. M. et al. Land use mix and physical activity in middle-aged and older adults: a longitudinal study examining changes in land use mix in two Dutch cohorts. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, v. 18, n. 1, 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-021-01083-1>.
42. Park, K. et al. The impacts of built environment characteristics of rail station areas on household travel behavior. *Cities*, v. 74, p. 277–283, 2018. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2017.12.015>.
43. Rosso, A. L. et al. Associations of neighborhood walkability and walking behaviors by cognitive trajectory in older adults. *The Gerontologist*, v. 61, n. 7, p. 1053–1061, 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/geront/gnaa110>.
44. Seong, E. Y.; Lee, N. H.; Choi, C. G. Relationship between land use mix and walking choice in high-density cities: a review of walking in Seoul, South Korea. *Sustainability*, v. 13, n. 2, p. 1–16, 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13020742>.
45. Sugiyama, T. et al. Land use proportion and walking: application of isometric substitution analysis. *Health & Place*, v. 57, p. 352–357, 2019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthplace.2019.03.003>.
46. Sun, Z. W. et al. Exploring the associations of walking behavior with neighborhood environments by different life stages: a cross-sectional study in a smaller Chinese city. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, v. 17, n. 1, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17010125>.
47. Sung, H.; Lee, S. Residential built environment and walking activity: empirical evidence of Jane Jacobs' urban vitality. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, v. 41, p. 318–329, 2015. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2015.09.009>.
48. Sung, H.; Lee, S.; Cheon, S. Operationalizing Jane Jacobs's urban design theory: empirical verification from the Great City of Seoul, Korea. *Journal of Planning Education and Research*, 2015. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739456X14568021>.
49. Sung, H.; Lee, S.; Jung, S. Identifying the relationship between the objectively measured built environment and walking activity in the high-density and transit-oriented city, Seoul, Korea. *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*, v. 41, n. 4, p. 637–660, 2014. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1068/b39116>.
50. Thornton, C. M. et al. Physical activity in older adults: an ecological approach. *Annals of Behavioral Medicine*, v. 51, n. 2, p. 159–169, 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12160-016-9837-1>.

51. Troped, P. J. et al. Direct and indirect associations between the built environment and leisure and utilitarian walking in older women. *Annals of Behavioral Medicine*, v. 51, n. 2, p. 282–291, 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12160-016-9852-2>.
52. Van Dyck, D. et al. Perceived neighborhood environmental attributes associated with adults' transport-related walking and cycling: findings from the USA, Australia, and Belgium. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, v. 9, n. 1, p. 70, 2012. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1479-5868-9-70>.
53. Vancampfort, D. et al. Associations of the built environment with physical activity and sedentary time in Ugandan outpatients with mental health problems. *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, v. 16, n. 4, p. 243–250, 2019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.2018-0200>.
54. Wang, J.; Cao, X. Exploring built environment correlates of walking distance of transit egress in the Twin Cities. *Journal of Transport Geography*, v. 64, p. 132–138, 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2017.08.013>.
55. Wang, Z.; Ettema, D.; Helbich, M. Objective environmental exposures correlate differently with recreational and transportation walking: a cross-sectional national study in the Netherlands. *Environmental Research*, v. 194, 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.110591>.
56. Wei, Y. et al. Walkability, land use and physical activity. *Sustainability*, v. 8, n. 1, p. 65, 2016. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8010065>.
57. Xiao, L. Z. et al. Built environment correlates of the propensity of walking and cycling. *Sustainability*, v. 12, n. 20, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12208304>.
58. Zandieh, R. et al. Do inequalities in neighborhood walkability drive disparities in older adults' outdoor walking? *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, v. 14, n. 7, p. 740, 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph14070740>.
59. Zang, P. et al. Eye-level street greenery and walking behaviors of older adults. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, v. 17, n. 17, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17176137>.
60. Zang, P.; Xue, C. Q. L.; Lu, Y.; Tu, K. W. Neighbourhood adaptability for Hong Kong's ageing population. *Urban Design International*, v. 24, n. 3, p. 187–205, 2019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41289-019-00086-1>.
61. Zhao, P.; Wan, J. Examining the effects of neighbourhood design on walking in a growing megacity. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, v. 86, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2020.102417>.

Appendix B: Number of studies by metric radii sizes and type of buffer.

Note. Studies with multiple radii sizes were counted multiple times.

Appendix C: tables of results

Table S1. Measures for the dependent variables. In parenthesis, the number of studies that adopted each type of measure.

Measure	Reference number (see Appendix A)
Total time spent walking (typically in minutes) in a specified amount of time (usually week or day). (20)	1; 8; 10; 11; 15; 28; 32; 34; 41; 46; 47; 49; 50; 53; 52; 55; 56; 58; 60; 61
Categorical variable (typically dichotomous) representing choice of walking versus other mode choice in trips made in the last X days. (9)	5; 7; 19; 26; 30; 33; 36; 48
Number of walking trips in a specified amount of time. (9)	4; 6; 12; 15; 18; 39; 42; 45; 61
Categorical variable (typically dichotomous) representing any walking (usually of 10 minutes or more) in a given period (typically 1 week). (8)	9; 17; 23; 28; 37; 42; 43; 51; 57
Categorical variable (typically dichotomous) representing choice of walking versus other mode choice for principal means of transportation. (7)	14; 13; 16; 20; 22; 44; 59
Categorical variable (typically dichotomous) representing whether an arbitrary minimum amount of time (typically 150 minutes) was spent walking in a specified amount of time (typically 1 week). (7)	3; 28; 31; 33; 38; 40; 47
Pedestrian counts. (4)	24; 25; 27; 29
Number of days per week with walking activity of at least 10 minutes. (3)	9; 47; 49
Distance walked between transit stops and non-home-ends. (1)	54
Walk share of each trip purpose. (1)	21
Percentage of people who use walking as their primary mode of transportation (1)	35

Table S2. Data sources for land use measures.

Land use data sources	Reference number (see Appendix A)
Official agencies	7; 10; 15; 19; 20; 18; 25; 26; 27; 29; 31; 32; 36; 38; 40; 44; 48; 49; 47; 50; 55; 56; 57; 58; 60; 61
Questionnaire (NEWS and its variants)	2; 1; 3; 6; 5; 8; 11; 12; 13; 16; 28; 35; 37; 39; 41; 45; 46; 51; 52; 59
Field surveys	3; 12; 14; 16; 17; 21; 22; 23; 24; 30; 33; 45; 46; 53; 59
Private agencies	37; 61
Previous studies	9
Google Street View	43
Not reported	4; 34; 33; 42; 54

Table S3. Land use categories for classifications of up to six uses.

Number of land use categories	Reference number (see Appendix A)
2 categories	
Category 1: agricultural, residential. Category 2: commercial, forest, industrial, public, rural.	19
Residential, nonresidential.	30; 29; 43; 47; 48
Stores, facilities.	51
3 categories	
Residential, retail, civic.	9
Residential, commercial, industrial / institutional.	15
Category 1: agricultural / residential; Category 2: commercial / industrial; Category 3: Forest / public / rural.	19
Residential, public [offices and institutions], commercial.	31
Residential, retail, office.	34
Residential, commercial and employment destinations, recreation	35
Convenience (i.e., convenience store, newsagent, or petrol station), supermarket, public transport stop	37
Commercial, residential, office.	22; 23; 60
Night uses (restaurants, bars, theaters, sports arenas), physical activity uses (parks, playgrounds, athletic properties), social uses (religious and cultural areas, playgrounds, athletic properties).	38
Residential, commercial, public.	42
Daily-activity neighborhood use, non-daily commercial use, office.	47
4 categories	
Residential, retail, commercial, industrial, others.	4
Category 1: agricultural / residential; Category 2: commercial / industrial; Category 3: forest / rural; Category 4: public.	19
Residential, commercial, recreational, institutional.	26
Residential, commercial/institutional, recreational and other	45
Residential, commercial, office, others.	24; 25; 44
Commercial, civic (education and hospital/medical), industrial, residential.	37
Residential, retail, office, recreational.	33
Residential, commercial, industrial, others.	36
Residential, commercial, industrial, recreational.	56
5 categories	

residential, commercial, educational, entertainment and public services	8
Residential, commercial, industrial/institutional, recreational, others.	15
Retail, commercial, civic, recreation (excluding public open space), residential	37
Residential, daily neighborhood life, non-daily use, office, others.	48
Residential, recre-ational, commercial, industrial, others.	55
Residential, retail (up to 90,000 m2), entertainment (including restaurants), office, institutional.	50
6 categories	
<hr/>	
Residential, commercial, office, public, recreational, others.	49
Residential, eating/drinking, green spaces, recreation centers, social infrastructure, retail.	58
Single family residential, multifamily residential, commercial, office, industrial, green space)	10
<hr/>	

Table S4. Spatial units used to aggregate land use mix variables.

Spatial units	Reference number (see Appendix A)
Areas (typically aerial or network buffers) around survey respondents' homes.	2; 3; 4; 6; 8; 9; 12; 13; 15; 20; 21; 22; 23; 33; 38; 40; 44; 45; 46; 47; 49; 50; 51 52; 28; 55; 56; 57; 58; 59; 61
Zones and administrative boundaries	11; 16; 17; 24; 30; 31; 32; 34; 33; 35; 36; 39; 48
Areas around origins, destinations and (sometimes) routes of trips.	5; 7; 14; 19; 18; 26; 53
Observation points along streets.	29
Areas around rail-based transit stations.	42
Areas around transit egresses	54

Table S5. Measures of land use mix.

Measures of Land Use Mix	Reference number (see Appendix A)
Evenness measures	
Shannon entropy with varying land use types (typically 3-6)	4; 5; 7; 8; 9; 10; 15; 16; 19; 20; 18; 21; 22; 23; 24; 25; 26; 27; 31; 32; 34; 33; 37; 41; 42; 44; 49; 47; 48; 50; 54; 55; 56; 57; 58; 59; 60; 61
Simpson's measure of evenness	19
Heip's index of evenness	19
Smith–Wilson evenness index	19
Bhat and Gossen land use mix diversity measure	19; 36; 18
Hill's ratio	19
Activity-related complementarity	18
Richness measures	
NEWS LUM Diversity: aggregate index representing how distant or close (as subjectively estimated by participants) are non-residential uses (typically 13) to participant's home.	2; 1; 3; 12; 14; 13; 17; 28; 39; 52; 46; 53
Number of different types of land uses within the spatial unit.	4; 38
Proxy measures	
NEWS LUM Access: Aggregate index representing the perception of how easy it is to get to non-residential uses and transit stops around participants' homes or workplace.	1; 11; 12; 14; 13; 17; 28; 51; 52; 53
Density or concentration of non-residential uses	23; 30; 33; 40; 48; 52; 56; 58
Proportion of non-residential uses: index of the type a/b, where "a" represents counts or total area of non-residential uses (typically retail) and "b" is the total count or area of all uses.	29; 37; 43; 45
Intensity of non-residential uses	38
Jobs-housing balance: ratio of jobs-to-housing units	18
Dichotomous variable representing census tract as job concentrator (most units are intended to run industrial or commercial activities, or institutional services) or mixed (more than one use, in a homogeneous proportion).	30
Sinergy measures	
Interaction measure: lines representing the interactions between two distinct uses	35
Composite (factor-based) measures	
Factor with three and five measures of land use mix or balance.	7
Land use mix construct: latent construct including composition and configuration of land uses	20

Notes. ^a This can be calculated through different methods: a) index of the type a/b, where "a" represents counts or total area of non-residential uses (typically retail) and "b" is the area of the spatial unit (typically the buffer) or the area of all other uses; b) clusters analysis capturing significant concentrations of non-residential uses in specific areas; c) average distances from each NR building to all other NR buildings.

Table S6. Direction and intensity of associations of LUM measures and the outcomes included in this study.

Association	Utilitarian walking	Leisure walking	Total/undefined walking
Positive association	1; 4; 7; 9; 10; 12; 13; 15; 16; 17; 21; 24; 26; 28 30; 31; 35; 36; 37; 38; 39; 50; 51; 55; 52	1; 30; 31; 51; 55	1; 3; 5; 8; 20; 18; 22; 25; 27; 32; 40; 41; 42; 43; 44; 45; 49; 48; 53; 57; 56; 59
Inconsistent association (positive and negative)	4; 19; 54; 61	14	20; 40; 47
Insignificant association	1; 28; 9; 15; 19; 23; 34; 33; 36; 38	23; 34; 33; 55	29; 32; 34; 41; 40; 49; 48; 56; 60
Negative association	30; 33	1; 33; 50	5; 11; 29; 46; 58

Table S7. Associations of LUM and dependent variables for the four most adopted LUM measures.

Measures	Direction of association	Utilitarian walking	Leisure walking	Total / undefined walking
Entropy ^a	Positive	4; 9; 10; 15; 16; 21; 24; 26; 31; 35; 37; 50; 55; 61	31; 55	8; 18; 22; 23; 25; 27; 32; 41; 42; 44; 49; 57; 59
	Inconsistent or insignificant	9; 15; 34; 48; 54	34	34; 5; 20; 47; 49; 56; 58; 60
	Negative	33	33; 50	11
NEWS LUM Diversity	Positive	2; 12; 13; 17; 28; 39; 52	-	3
	Inconsistent or insignificant	1	1; 14	1; 2
	Negative	-	-	46
NEWS LUM Access	Positive	1; 12; 13; 17; 28; 52; 51	51	6; 53
	Inconsistent or insignificant	2	1; 14	1; 14
	Negative	-	-	-
Density of non-residential uses ^b	Positive	51; 52; 38	-	-
	Inconsistent or insignificant	33; 30	33	40
	Negative	-	-	-

Notes. ^a Includes weighted entropy; ^b Includes retail density (He et al. 2020).

Appendix D: Entropy formula (Frank et al., 2005)

$$D_E = -\frac{\sum_i^N p_i \cdot \ln(p_i)}{\ln(N)}$$

Where:

D_E = Entropy measure of diversity.

p_i = proportion of use i .

N = total number of uses.